

EVIDENCE REPORT

In response to the EU Call for Evidence for an Initiative: Union of Equality: 2026-2030
LGBTIQ Equality Strategy

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COUNTRY FOCUS:

Poland

SUMMARY:

Human rights relating to gender and sexuality in Poland are negatively impacted by widespread, systematic “anti-gender” mobilizations, with NGOs and education professionals taking the lead in countering them, while the state falls behind and oftentimes itself directly contributes to the discrimination on the SOGIESC grounds, perpetuating exclusions of children, youth, and adults belonging to the minoritised groups.

Poland’s sociopolitical climate presents challenges to SOGIESC-inclusive, democratic governance, as well as to the wholistic wellbeing of LGBTIQ+ persons, as conservative “anti-gender” actors equate gender expression with “gender ideology”, LGBTIQ+ identities and experiences with “homopropaganda” or “LGBT agenda”, and sex education with the “sexualization of children”. Consequently, inclusive education workshops and self-help resources are mainly provided by non-governmental organizations and individual education professionals.

Poland is heavily impacted by the ‘anti-gender’ politics. **RESIST Report on Poland** ([Kulpa and Kania, 2025](#)) shows that **common experiences** are that of bullying and intimidation, and of systemic, institutional discrimination. Social media are a popular platform where much of the hateful language and attitudes is experienced. Public institutions fail to adequately address the issues of gender and sexual diversity. Oftentimes officers and administrators lack language and knowledge to address individual cases, nor can use policies and regulations as these are largely non-existent.

Produced effects concern psychological burnouts and depletions among participants, who highlight high emotional costs of everyday dealing with discriminatory and hateful atmosphere. There are clear negative impacts on the mental health and general wellbeing of minoritised communities in Poland, who are predominantly target of the ‘anti-gender’ politics in Poland. Other observed effects are e.g. fearful self-censorship, where people actively hide some information to avoid self-exposure to potential discriminatory attitudes. There were also more grave instances of harms to bodies and property reported.

However, it was also noted that **‘anti-gender’ politics have produced some ‘ricochet effects’** such as greater social mobilisation for the queer-feminist causes. It was noted that social attitudes are positively changing towards greater acceptance and support for minoritised groups. People multiply marginalised and minoritised due to their intersectional positionalities are usually more adversely affected and tend to prioritise other needs than those related to their gendered and sexual identities, which are perceived as secondary to other problems they face or are committed to changing.

Our participants have been **navigating ‘anti-gender’ impacts** on their lives in different ways: these can be shielding away and withdrawing, or conversely, remobilising. Strong ethos of community support and mutual care and solidarity practices was also clearly pronounced as a common way of coping with the pressures of ‘anti-gender’ politics.

Key takeaways:

- 1) The EU commitment and promotion of equal rights for all is of key importance to support civil society in enshrining LGBTIQ+ rights into policy solutions, legal frameworks, political culture, and daily lives of SOGIESC communities at local, regional, national, and international levels.
- 2) SOGIESC-inclusive education in Poland is stunted by “anti-gender” mobilizations, which frame any discussion of gender and sexuality as “gender ideology” and “LGBT agenda”, threatening children and young people.
- 3) LGBTIQ+ persons in Poland are threatened by direct interference from conservative and far-right political and religious figures.
- 4) SOGIESC-inclusive initiatives aimed at improving the mental health of LGBTIQ+ populations in Poland are primarily driven by non-governmental organizations and education professionals who work to transform their institutions into welcoming and safe spaces, despite facing state pressures to limit diversity-promoting, SOGIESC-inclusive education.
- 5) The state protection of minoritised communities on the SOGIESC grounds is critically inadequate. EU LGBTIQ Strategy was critical in supporting PL state in introducing certain anti-discriminatory protections, but “anti-gender” mobilisations (both political, media, and civil society) pose a significant threat to the effective implementation of such policies and reforms, actively stalling advancements.
- 6) Evidence from the individual research of the authors of this Evidence Submission as well as that of the RESIST Project, and other, clearly shows that there is a continuous need for the European Commission to continue working on a renewed LGBTIQ equality strategy for the upcoming years, to combat the inequalities experienced by LGBTIQ people.

Recommendations:

- 1) **Address hate speech by public officials and elected representatives:** there is a need of political accountability mechanisms at EU and national level, especially within the European Parliament, to hold the public figures accountable for using and promoting hate speech and misinformation.
- 2) **Comprehensive education on gender and sexual diversity combined with education on “anti-gender” movements:** Raising awareness about gender and sexual diversity, as well as the manifestations, tactics, and effects of “anti-gender” politics, is essential for fostering more educated and open societies. Education about the negative impacts of “anti-gender” efforts to suppress gender and sexual diversity, and the toll they take on people’s lives, can promote understanding and acceptance.
- 3) **Strengthen legal and institutional protections:** Ensure effective and harmonised implementation of the Violence Against Women Directive, Victims’ Rights Directive, and EU anti-discrimination legislation, ensuring that LGBTQI people in intersectional positions are included in the implementation processes.
- 4) **International funding schemes to ensure continuous and long-lasting impact, regardless of shifting political landscapes:** Organisations and educators in Poland working to create safe spaces for LGBTIQ+ people face underfunding and cannot rely on state support due to the prevailing anti-LGBTIQ+ climate. This lack of resources hampers their ability to implement effective programs and initiatives.
- 5) **Support EU-wide initiatives to promote journalistic ethics & counter disinformation:** and regulate online hate speech & violence through existing digital and media legislation (e.g. Digital Services Act, Code of Practice on Disinformation).
- 6) **Systematic, inclusive, data to underpin social policies:** National and governmental institutions in the fields of education, health and well-being, should develop a comprehensive and systematic mode of collecting SOGIESC-disaggregated data to understand the effects of social change on SOGIESC minoritised groups.
- 7) **Promote EU-wide minimum standards:** esp. for defining and prosecuting hate crimes targeting LGBTIQ+ persons, aligned with the proposed inclusion of hate crime and hate speech in the list of EU crimes (Article 83 TFEU).
- 8) **Recognise “anti-gender” mobilisations as a systemic threat:** “Anti-gender” mobilisations should be recognised as a component of democratic backsliding and disinformation that poses a threat to fundamental EU values. Utilise EU Rule of Law Mechanisms (e.g. Article 7 TEU procedures, Rule of Law Framework, Conditionality Regulation) to address systemic violations linked to “anti-gender” policies.

Explanation & Evidence:

Q1: Does your country have any school policies or curricula regarding the recognition of SOGIESC diversity?

Education on gender and sexuality in Polish schools is in a dire state. Changes in school curriculum are under way, but can be halted by conservative movements.

A 2023 report by Grupa Ponton, an NGO comprised of sex educators, surveyed 10,730 individuals aged 13 to 22 to assess the quality of the so-called “Education for family life,” an extra-curricular school subject that is the closest approximation to sex education. **90% of young respondents reported that their “Education for family life” classes did not address psychosexual orientation, while 94% had not learned about gender identity.** Topics such as sexual violence, psychological violence, domestic violence, and sources of support were similarly overlooked, with neglect reported in 73%, 69%, 66%, and 57% of cases, respectively ([Grupa Ponton 2023](#) [in Polish]).

“Education for family life”, starting at ages 10-11 and requiring parental consent for underage students, is notorious for perpetuating gender stereotypes and inadequately addressing LGBTIQ+ identities ([Chmura-Rutkowska et al. 2016 for Fundacja Feminoteka](#) [in Polish]). This is further exacerbated by a lack of progressive gender and sexual representation in Polish textbooks across all subjects ([Chmura-Rutkowska et al. 2016](#)) and in Polish children’s and adolescent literature ([Zabrzewska 2023](#)).

With the Ministry of Education currently under Minister Barbara Nowacka (from the center-left Polish Initiative), “Education for family life” will be replaced in September 2025 by “Health education,” which aims to include SOGI-inclusive sex education. These plans are already met with contestation from the conservative Catholic “pro-life” organizations (e.g. [Coalition for the Salvation of Polish Schools](#)). This pressure has already led Minister Nowacka to reclassify “Health education” from a curricular subject to an extracurricular one (i.e. non-compulsory), at least in its first year of existence.

Q2: Do any laws, policies, or practices in your country shape SOGIESC-diverse persons’ ability to fully realize their right to identity?

- 1) **Yes, negatively. Polish “anti-gender” landscape, as examined by the EU-funded [RESIST Project](#), is both crucial and harmful to the situation of SOGIESC-diverse people in Poland, impacting local policies and practices.** This is because:
 - a) “Anti-gender” actors position themselves as defenders of Polish ethnic and national identity, Catholic values, and the traditional heteronormative family ([RESIST Project Team, 2024a](#)), implicitly treating children and women as instruments of national continuity rather than autonomous subjects capable of self-determination.
 - b) “Anti-gender” politics promotes an image of youth as vulnerable to “sexualization’ and ideological indoctrination, fostering panic around sex and relationships education and portraying it as a danger to the impressionable young adults ([RESIST Project Team, 2024b](#)).

- c) “Anti-gender” actors use the concept of “sexualization” to attack not only feminist critiques of gender roles, ineffective (sexual) education, and LGBTIQ+ activism but also the rights of transgender individuals to bodily autonomy and self-determination ([RESIST Project Team, 2024b](#)), ultimately hindering the progress of SOGIESC-inclusive education, leaving LGBTIQ+ people vulnerable to discrimination and marginalization.
- 2) **Yes, negatively. The struggle for SOGIESC-diverse education in Poland has faced significant challenges, particularly from the politicians advocating “anti-gender” ideologies.** These efforts have fostered a hostile environment that places pressure on both educators and students, undermining the fundamental principles of inclusivity and acceptance in educational settings.
- a) Polish participants of the RESIST Project’s study on the effects of, and strategies against “anti-gender” mobilizations ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)), have reported a permissive atmosphere for political extortion, unjustified influence, and intimidation at a structural level. They noted that e.g. schools that are recognized as LGBTIQ-friendly faced maliciously-intended scrutiny and inspections from authorities, further stifling efforts to create inclusive environments ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#))
- b) RESIST Project’s research participants based in Poland spoke about limitations to the academic freedoms on secondary and higher education levels ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)). One example given is about a bishop calling a university rector to express discontent, leaving the rector uncertain about how to navigate the pressure. In another case, a rector’s plenipotentiary for equal treatment was dismissed overnight for promoting a support system for transgender individuals. Research participant Ania highlights the chilling effects of intimidation actions within educational institutions, recalling:
- [a] year later, my school [name] was featured in a speech by the Children's Ombudsman [Mikołaj Pawlak] because of the 'outrageous thing' of being highly ranked as an LGBT-friendly school, and the Children's Ombudsman sent another inspection to the school ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#), pp. 9-10).
- Mikołaj Pawlak, elected by the then ruling conservative right-wing party Law and Justice, served as Children’s Ombudsman from 2018 to 2023.
- c) Former Minister of Education, Przemysław Czarnek (Law and Justice party), known for his homophobic declarations, has made attempts during his time in the office (2020-2023) at passing laws that would limit LGBTIQ+ freedoms in schools, banning queer-feminist CSOs/NGOs from the educational institutions (see articles on “Lex Czarnek” from the [PinkNews](#) and The [European Conservative](#)). Przemysław Czarnek was also infamously against Rainbow Fridays [Tęczowe Piątki], the main SOGI-inclusive initiative in Polish schools, initiated in 2016 by Campaign Against Homophobia (KPH) and now continued by [Fundacja GrowSpace](#).

- 3) Experiences of Polish educators in higher education institutions, collected during the RESIST Project's research, reveal that HEI implement equality measures for legal compliance, such as adhering to the EU regulations on Gender Equality Plans, and not for the actual EDI-minded policy and culture change.
- a) On the positive side, those engaged in SOGIESC equalities often leverage these measures to create a more meaningful impact, e.g. to raise awareness about gender-based violence ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#), p. 12). It is likely that similar mechanisms could be applied to education at lower levels.

Q3: Do any laws, policies, or practices in your country shape SOGIESC-diverse persons' ability to fully realize their right to identity?

In the absence of state-level policies governing people's rights to express their gender identity through chosen names, institutions are left to navigate the complexities of trans and non-binary identities independently. Consequently, much relies on the goodwill, knowledge, and sensitivity of the educators. RESIST Project's participant quotes:

POLINT1: [T]hey're just dazed and confused. They don't know how to do it. [...] The directors were super supportive but terrified. They did not know how to implement it. This was all happening during you-know-which government [Law and Justice] so I assume this was where their [institution] fears were coming from. [...] But they weren't unwilling. They [the institution] started cooperating immediately. But I had the suspicion they needed a small push. [...] **Communication-wise, this was a very good experience and while [the institution] structurally is not ready for it, there's strong support from individual people.**

Other reports testify to the experiences of discrimination and marginalization of transgender Poles. [Campaign Against Homophobia \(KPH\)](#) and [Lambda](#)'s report on the social situation LGBTIQ+ persons in Poland during the years 2019-2020 ([Sytuacja społeczna osob LGBTA. Raport za lata 2019-2020 \[in Polish\]](#)) established that:

- **Among transgender individuals who came out to their parents, 40.4% have fully accepting fathers and 47.7% have fully accepting mothers. 23% reported losing at least one close person after coming out.**
- 13.6% of transgender individuals were kicked out of their homes and 4.4% experienced homelessness in the past year.
- 20% received suggestions for "treatment" or "fixing" their gender identity from mental health support providers.

Q4: Is there available national or institutional disaggregated data on health? Is this data disaggregated by sexual orientation and/or gender identity?

In Poland, the lack of state support for the mental well-being of adults esp. in relation to SOGIESC identities is a pressing concern. Existing data suggests a critical mental health crisis among LGBTIQ+ population in Poland, with high rates of suicidal thoughts and feelings of loneliness, and minimal institutional support especially among youth.

Research on child and adolescent health is carried out by the NGO [Fundacja Dajemy Dzieciom Siłę](#). Their 2022 report [Dzieci się liczą](#) [Children count; in Polish] has a qualitative section on the impacts of SOGIESC-based discrimination on child and adolescent mental health. For the quantitative part, it cites: 2015-2016 report by KPH, Lambda, and Trans-Fuzja Foundation; and the 2019-2020 by KPH and Lambda, which covered participants under the age of 18 (Polish legal age). The reports can be accessed here (in Polish):

- [Sytuacja społeczna osób LGBTQA w Polsce. Raport za lata 2015-2016](#)
- [Sytuacja społeczna osob LGBTQA. Raport za lata 2019-2020](#)

The 2015-2016 survey revealed that 69.4% of LGBT individuals under 18 reported having suicidal thoughts, with nearly 12% stating this occurs frequently. **The 2019-2020 report revealed that 74.29% of LGBTIQ+ teenagers felt lonely, and 75% reported having suicidal thoughts**, with only a small percentage receiving institutional support.

Fundacja Dajemy Dzieciom Siłę also runs a 24/7 helpline for children and adolescents, which relies on government and grant funding for 30-60% of its budget. In late 2021, when the conservative Law and Justice government announced plans to cut funding, the helpline's existence was placed in jeopardy, despite its significant positive impact. Over 13 years of operation, the [helpline](#) has received more than 1.4 million calls, responded to over 92,000 messages, and conducted more than 3,300 interventions in situations threatening the health or life of a child. This situation underscores the precarious nature of relying on government funding in shifting political landscapes.